

INTERVIEW GUIDE
VASECTOMY PROVIDERS

Thank you again for taking the time to talk to me. I am interested in learning about your vasectomy practice and particularly how you make decisions around complex cases.

Close-ended questionnaire

How old are you? ENTER RESPONSE	__ __ years old
What is your gender? CIRCLE ONE ANSWER (<u>DO NOT</u> READ OPTIONS)	Female.....01 Male.....02 Transgender female.....03 Transgender male.....04 Gender non-confirming / non-binary.....05 Other.....88 Prefer not to say.....99
What race or ethnicity do you identify as? CIRCLE ONE ANSWER (<u>DO NOT</u> READ OPTIONS)	White.....01 Hispanic, Latino, or Spanish origin.....02 Black or African American.....03 Asian.....04 American Indian or Alaska Native.....05 Middle Eastern or North African.....06 Native Hawaiian or Pacific Islander.....07 Other.....88 Prefer not to say.....99
How many years have you been performing vasectomies? ENTER RESPONSE IN YEARS	__ __ years
What country do you perform vasectomies in? ENTER RESPONSE	
What is the average number of vasectomies that you perform each month? ENTER RESPONSE IN VASECTOMIES PER MONTH	__ __ __ __ vasectomies/month
What is your training degree? CIRCLE ONE ANSWER (<u>DO NOT</u> READ OPTIONS)	MD.....01 RN.....02 NP.....03 PA.....04 DO.....05 Other:_____
What is your specialization? ENTER RESPONSE	

Warm up

1. To get started, can you tell me how you got involved in providing vasectomies?
 - a. Probe: How long have you been doing it?
 - b. Probe: What made you decide to get involved in vasectomies?
 - c. Probe: What is the best thing about being a vasectomist?
 - d. Probe: What do you find most challenging about being a vasectomist?

2. I want you to think back to when you first learned the vasectomy technique ___ years ago. What type of training did you receive?
 - a. Probe: What information did it include? Who performed the training? Where was it?
 - b. Probe: What didactic training did you receive? Who performed that piece of the training?
 - c. Probe: What about practical training?
 - d. Probe: What training did you receive around informed consent?
 - e. Probe: Were there other components of the training?

Vignettes

3. Great, thank you for that background/context. Now I want to spend a little bit of time talking about some hypothetical cases. I'm going to provide some brief information about men coming for vasectomies and hear what you'd recommend as a physician. Would you provide the vasectomy, deny the vasectomy, or need more information? There is no right or wrong answer. Again, I am simply trying to understand how providers navigate complex and challenging cases.

Probes: What are some of the factors that are particularly important to consider when deciding whether or not to provide a vasectomy?

Probes: How important is (possibility of regret, age, marital status, number of living children, age of living children, chance of malpractice lawsuit)?

Probe: Could you explain why these factors are important to consider when deciding whether or not to provide a vasectomy?

 - a. *A 24-year-old man presents for vasectomy. No kids, dating monogamously but not married. He says he has never wanted kids because of overpopulation and climate change.*

 - b. *A 30-year-old man with a wife and two children presents for a vasectomy. His wife is currently pregnant. They always planned on having no more than three children.*

 - c. *A 50-year-old recently divorced man presents for a vasectomy. He and his ex-wife have two grown children. His ex-wife had a tubal ligation, but now that he's*

single, he wants to eliminate his chance of another pregnancy. He would like to remarry at some point.

- d. *A 37-year-old man presents for a vasectomy. He is visibly uncomfortable about the idea of the procedure, and expresses some hesitancy.*
 - *What if he mentions he's not sure he wants a vasectomy, but that his wife had serious complications during the birth of their third child and it would be a threat to her life if she were to become pregnant again? She has also had bad reactions to hormonal birth control and does not consider it an option. He knows it's the right thing, but doesn't want to do it. What if you have seen the patient be pressured by his wife during the consultation?*

- e. *A 34-year-old man presents for a vasectomy. On his medical history form, he lists lithium, a mood stabilizer, as a medication he is currently taking, but does not disclose any disorders. [Bi-polar disorder]*

Decision-making for cases and informed consent

Great so next I want to spend a bit of time talking about your personal experience making decisions about and performing vasectomies. [If they don't come up naturally during the vignettes]

- 4. Thinking back on your career, what is one challenging case you've encountered, where you weren't sure if you should provide the vasectomy? This does not include clinical challenges, like pre-vasectomy pain syndrome. Please describe the case.
 - a. Probe: Did you perform the vasectomy? Why or why not?
 - b. Probe: How did you come to a decision? What factors did you consider? Did any training you previously received help inform your decision? Did previous cases inform your decision?
 - c. Probe: What conversations did you have with the patient? How did you counsel them?

- 5. What's another complicated case you have encountered? Please describe the case.
 - a. Probe: What other strategies did you use to handle it?
 - b. Probe: Have you ever used mentors or the google group for decision-making?

- 6. Can you think of a time when you had a difficult time getting informed consent?
 - a. Probe: What made it challenging? How did you overcome the challenge?

Training

Lastly, I want to wrap up by talking about your training background, and processes used in your office, and how you all have navigated COVID-19.

7. What training did you receive on ethics in vasectomy provision?
 - a. Probe: How were you trained to employ the principles of “do no harm” in vasectomy provision?
 - b. Probe: Were there other ethical principles that were part of your training?
 - c. Probe: Did your training come to bear in navigating decision-making around complicated cases? If so, how? If not, what has been useful in navigating decision-making that you learned elsewhere?

8. How do you collect informed consent in your office?
 - a. Probes: What is the process? Who is involved? Is there a specific form? What information is provided? Is it the same for every person (i.e., standardized)?

9. How has your office been impacted by COVID-19?
 - a. How have you responded to those impacts? Has the counseling process changed? What about the consent process? Has your client volume load changed?

10. What would you recommend to a newly practicing physician providing vasectomies?

11. Is there anything else you would like to add?